

Similarly, other compounds were prepared using different anilines (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF 4/6-CHLORO-3-(SUBSTITUTED-PHENYLIMINO)-2-INDOLINONES (3-5)*

Sl. no.**	Compd. no.	R	X	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
1.	3a	Cl	-	57	197-200	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
2.	4a	H	-	64	225	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₂ O
3.	4a	Cl	-	71	240	C ₁₄ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
4.	4a	OCH ₃	-	60	185-90	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂
5.	5a	H	CH ₂	66	165	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O
6.	5a	Cl	O	68	165	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂
7.	5a	Cl	CH ₂	63	165-67	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂
8.	5a	OCH ₃	O	62	128-30	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂
9.	5a	OCH ₃	CH ₂	67	125	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂
10.	3b	Cl	-	57	144	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
11.	4b	H	-	71	190	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₂ O
12.	4b	Cl	-	68	220-22	C ₁₄ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
13.	4b	OCH ₃	-	66	218	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂
14.	5b	H	O	59	210d	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂
15.	5b	H	CH ₂	56	220d	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O
16.	5b	Cl	O	73	147	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂
17.	5b	Cl	CH ₂	62	170	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
18.	5b	OCH ₃	O	60	158	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂
19.	5b	OCH ₃	CH ₂	62	195	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂

*Satisfactory C, H analysis were obtained for all the compounds.

**For sl. nos. 1-9, Y = 4-Cl; for sl. nos. 10-19, Y = 6-Cl.

6-Chloro-3-(substituted-phenylimino)-2-indolinones (4b): The compounds were prepared by using 6-chloroisatin and different anilines (Table 1).⁵

4-Chloro-1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-3-(substituted-phenylimino)-2-indolinones (5a): 4-Chloro-3-substituted-phenylimino-2-indolinone (0.01 mol) was suspended in methanol (20 ml) and warmed on a water-bath and then formalin (1 ml) and morpholine (1 ml) were added to it with vigorous stirring and kept at room temperature overnight. The resulting solid was washed with methanol, dried and recrystallised from CHCl₃-petroleum ether (b.p. 80-100°).

Similarly, other morpholino/piperidinomethyl analogs were synthesised; ν_{max} compd. sl. no. 5: 2920 (CH₂), 1730 (C=O), 1600 (C=N) and 790 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 6: 2940 (CH₂), 1740 (C=O), 1600 (C=N) and 790 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 7: 2940 (CH₂), 1730 (C=O), 1600 (C=N) and 770 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 8: δ 2.43 (4H, N (CH₂)₂), 3.52 (4H, O(CH₂)₂), 4.21 (2H, NCH₂N) and 6.78-7.22 (7H, ArH); compd. sl. no. 9: δ 2.50 (4H, N(CH₂)₂), 3.60 (4H, O(CH₂)₂), 3.78 (3H, OCH₃), 4.32 (2H, NCH₂N) and 6.8-7.3 (7H, ArH); compd. sl. no. 10: δ 2.40 (4H, N(CH₂)₂), 3.70 (3H, OCH₃), 4.22 (2H, NCH₂N) and 6.7-7.2 (7H, ArH).

6-Chloro-1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-3-(substituted-phenylimino)-2-indolinones (5b): The compounds were prepared by the above method using 6-chloro-3-(substituted-phenylimino)-2-indolinones (Table 1); ν_{max} compd. sl. no. 16: 2840 (CH₂),

1725 (C=O), 1595 (C=N) and 850 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 17: 2910 (CH₂), 1730 (C=O), 1590 (C=N) and 820 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 18: 2840 (CH₂), 1710 (C=O), 1580 (C=N) and 830 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 19: 2940 (CH₂), 1720 (C=O), 1610 (C=N) and 820 cm⁻¹ (CCl)

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head of Chemistry Department for facilities. Thanks are also due to Dr. R. S. Kapil and Prof. S. P. Singh for analytical and spectral data.

Reference

- R. S. VARMA and P. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 802.

Synthesis of some New Isonicotinoylazopyrazoles

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Manuscript received 26 October 1988, revised 8 February 1989, accepted 2 February 1989

THE chemistry of isoniazide and pyrazoles has been very extensively studied because many drugs include these rings¹. Similarly, biological importance of azo compounds is well-known². In

the light of the promising pharmacological activities exhibited by pyrazole nucleus, isoniazide and azo group, it was considered worthwhile to combine these moieties in order to enhance the overall activity of the resulting molecule.

N-Isonicotinoyl-3-phenylamino-5-methyl-4-(2'-chloro)phenylamino; -4-arylazopyrazoles (3) have been synthesised by diazotising various substituted-anilines and coupling the diazotised products with the compounds having active methylene group, viz. 4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-dione (1) and 4-(2'-chlorophenyl)aminobutane-2,4-dione (2) followed by condensation with isonicotinoylhydrazine (isoniazide).

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Specord Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer, and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a R-35 Perkin-Elmer instrument using TMS as internal standard. All the melting points are uncorrected.

2-Arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione : Appropriate aniline derivative (0.95 ml, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid (3 ml) and water (4 ml) and cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. To it, cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.01 mol) was added in small portions maintaining the temperature at 0°. The resulting diazonium salt was filtered in already cooled solution mixture of 1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione (1.8 g, 0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (8.2 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml, 0.4 mol). The solid so obtained (1) was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

Another series of the hydrazones (2) were synthesised by taking 4-(2'-chloro)phenylaminobutane-2,4-dione instead of 4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-dione.

***N*-Isonicotinoyl-3-phenylamino-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles** : To 2-arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione (0.001 mol, 0.281 g) dissolved in acetic acid (10–15 ml), a solution of isoniazide (0.001 mol, 0.137 g) in acetic acid (15–20 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed for 6 h, and then allowed to cool overnight. The resulting shining crystals were recrystallised from ethanol, m p 80° (Found : C, 69.01; N, 21.78. C₂₂H₁₈N₆O calcd. for : C, 69.10; N, 21.98%); λ_{max} (CH₃OH) 234, 252 and 370 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 1590 (N=N), 1620 (C=O) and 3120 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (CDCl₃) 2.76 (3H, CH₃), 11.37 (H, NHC₅H₅) and 7.1–7.8 (14H, Ar).

Similarly, other derivatives of *N*-isonicotinoyl-3-phenylamino-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles were prepared by taking suitable coupled product having substituents, viz. 3-Cl, 4-Cl, 2-CH₃, 4-CH₃, 2-OCH₃, 2-NO₂, 3-NO₂, 4-NO₂, 4-Br, and 2-NO₂, 4-CH₃ (Table 1).

Similarly, one more series of *N*-isonicotinoyl-3-phenylamino-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles were prepared by using 2-arylhydrazono-1-(2'-chloro)phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione instead of 2-arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione (Table 1), m p. 124° (Found : C, 63.16; N, 20.00. C₂₂H₁₇N₆OCl calcd. for : C, 63.38; N, 20.16%); λ_{max} (CH₃OH) 235, 250 and 380 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 1580 (N=N), 1640 (C=N), 1660 (CO) and 3150 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (CDCl₃) 2.30 (3H, CH₃), 11.10 (H, NHC₅H₅) and 7.15–7.70 (13H, Ar).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF *N*-ISONICOTINOYL-3-PHENYLAMINO-5-METHYL-4-ARYLAZOPYRAZOLES*

Sl. no.	R	R'	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Colour	λ _{max}
1.	H	H	70	80	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₆ O	Yellow	234, 252, 370
2.	2-CH ₃	H	65	158	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₆ O	Green	236, 255, 385
3.	4-CH ₃	H	65	125	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₆ O	Green	233, 257, 375
4.	2-NO ₂	H	60	195	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂	Brown	233, 252, 370
5.	3-NO ₂	H	65	190	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂	Yellowish green	237, 254, 370
6.	4-NO ₂	H	62	215	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂	Dark brown	239, 253, 370
7.	2-OCH ₃	H	60	127	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂	Green	231, 254, 375
8.	3-Cl	H	55	130	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₆ OCl	Light yellow	237, 254, 380
9.	4-Cl	H	60	136	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₆ OCl	Green	237, 257, 380
10.	4-Br	H	65	140	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₆ OBr	Green	234, 258, 385
11.	2-NO ₂ , 4-CH ₃	H	60	190	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₂	Dark brown	230, 255, 380
12.	H	2-Cl	65	124	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₆ OCl	Yellow	235, 250, 380
13.	2-CH ₃	2-Cl	60	158	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₆ OCl	Yellow	248, 254, 380
14.	2-NO ₂ , 4-CH ₃	2-Cl	60	150	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₆ OCl	Yellow	238, 252, 385
15.	2-NO ₂	2-Cl	65	205	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₂ Cl	Yellow	230, 255, 380
16.	3-NO ₂	2-Cl	65	201	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₂ Cl	Yellow	248, 254, 380
17.	4-NO ₂	2-Cl	70	225	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₂ Cl	Greenish brown	238, 252, 380
18.	2-OCH ₃	2-Cl	55	155	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₆ O ₂ Cl	Yellow	232, 254, 390
19.	3-Cl	2-Cl	55	142	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₆ OCl ₂	Light yellow	238, 254, 370
20.	4-Cl	2-Cl	60	170	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₆ OCl ₂	Yellow	234, 256, 370
21.	4-Br	2-Cl	55	185	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₆ OClBr	Yellow	236, 254, 380

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. R. P. Bhatnagar, Head of the Department for facilities.

References

1. H. N. FOX, *Science*, 1952, 116, 129; R. B. PATHAK and S. C. BAHEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 1108; T. IRIKUPA, Jap. Pat. 7 570 367/1975 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, 84, 59445); U. WRZECIONO, K. PIETKIEWIEZ and B. KRZYAZTO, *Pharmazie*, 1978, 33, 266; J. F. W. MCOMIE and R. N. FIMMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 92.
2. R. G. CHILD, R. G. WILKINSON and A. T. FUCIK, US Pat. 4 006 234/1977 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, 87, 6031); I. M. ROUSHADI, E. S. A. IBRAHIM and H. S. HABIB, *Pharmazie*, 1956, 31, 856; K. N. GAIND and J. M. KHANNA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1964, 26, 34; L. S. GOODMAN and A. GILMAN, "The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", 4th. ed., Macmillan, New York, 1970, p. 1111; J. L. EVERETT and W. C. J. ROSS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1972.
3. R. JAIN and P. PANDEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.

Synthesis of some New Fluorinated Derivatives of 1,3,5-Triazine as Potential Biologically Active Agents

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Manuscript received 26 October 1988, revised 6 February 1989, accepted 21 February 1989

SOME 1,3,5-triazine derivatives have been reported to exhibit interesting biological activities¹. In view of the biological activity, we have synthesised (Scheme 1) and characterised a number of new 2-(arylanilino)-4-(2-chloro-5-trifluoromethylani- lino)-6-(3-nitroanilino)-1,3,5-triazine derivatives

Scheme 1

These compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* by paper disc method². All the compounds exhibited significant activity against *S. aureus*, however, no activity against *E. coli* (Table 1).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected, and the purity was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹⁹F nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆; TMS as an internal standard for ¹H and C₆F₆ as an external standard for ¹⁹F) on a FX 93Q JEOL spectrometer (90 MHz).

2,4-Dichloro-6-(3-nitroanilino)-1,3,5-triazine (1): To 2,4,6-trichloro-1,3,5-triazine (5.53 g, 0.03 mol) dissolved in acetone (30 ml) was added a solution of *m*-nitroaniline (4.14 g, 0.03 mol) in acetone (10 ml) with stirring at 0–5° followed by the addition of NaOH solution (1.2 g, 0.03 mol in 10 ml of water). The reaction mixture was stirred for further 3 h at 0–5°. It was then poured into ice-cold water and acidified with HCl. The resulting solid was washed,

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Sl. no.	Ar	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Zone of inhibition (mm) <i>S. aureus</i>
1.	<i>p</i> -COOH C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₄	158	60	7.0
2.	<i>m</i> -COOH C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₄	180	61	6.0
3.	<i>m</i> -Cl C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ F ₃ N ₇ O ₂	160	90	6.0
4.	<i>m</i> -OH C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₃	145	60	8.0
5.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₄	210	70	7.0
6.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₂	115	65	7.0
7.	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₂	118	60	7.0
8.	C ₁₀ H ₇	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₂	190	61	6.0
9.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₂	202	63	7.0
10.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₄	220	60	7.0

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.